

**STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF VEHICLE ACTIVITY ON THE ROUTE IN ANDIJAN
REGION**

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Annotation: It is considered very important to maintain and optimize the technical condition of the rolling stock, to improve the technology of efficient use of the rolling stock in order to increase the efficiency of the work of passenger-carrying ATK in the Andijan region, and in the organization of these works, to organize the work of the TXK and T, as well as the control departments of the ATK with high quality, concrete proposals for modernization and improvement of the technical base of the general enterprise are given.

Key words: motor vehicle, rolling stock, regulation, competence, qualification, passenger transportation, cargo transportation, technical parameter, technical base, technical service.

Passenger transportation and passenger turnover in Andijan region by road transport in January-June 2023, 347.8 million people were transported by all types of road transport, this figure is 103.5% compared to the same period last year. formed During this period, the growth rate of passenger traffic reached 107.0% and made 6,390.5 million passenger-km.

In large cities around the world, the quality indicators of public transportation services, including the issues of getting passengers to their destinations on time and in comfort, modern solutions to existing problems, and improving the quality of service, are becoming important. . In this regard, special attention is paid to the development of new scientific and technical solutions for improving the quality of city bus services in developed foreign countries, including the USA, England, Germany, France, Singapore, Japan, and South Korea. Motor transport network enterprises are involved in the process of passenger transportation as the main subject.[1]

In our republic, large-scale work is being carried out to develop motor transport network enterprises, to raise the quality of the provided service to the level of world standards, and to increase work efficiency. In particular, as a result of passengers staying on the roads for a long time, great material damage is caused to the economy of our country.[2]

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 10, 2017 "On measures to provide public transport services and further improve the system of passenger transportation by buses in cities and villages" (PQ2724) and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Pursuant to the decision of March 6, 2019 PQ-4230 "On measures to radically improve the cargo and passenger transportation system", further improvement of the system of organization of transport services, for carriers of all forms of ownership many goals and tasks have been defined in terms of creating a competitive environment and favorable conditions and increasing the transport and transit potential of the Republic[3].

Based on the decision, the "Roadmap" on "Further development of passenger and cargo transportation" was approved, and on the basis of this, effective work is being carried out on the development of the sector. The problem of providing urban residents with transport becomes especially important in the conditions of our republic's economic growth. It is impossible to increase the production of goods and services without the appropriate development of passenger transport in industrial centers.

In addition, the stabilization of economic development leads to an increase in the well-being of the working population, which in turn determines the demands of passengers for the quality of transport[4].

Here, in 2019, if we analyze the data provided by the statistics committee on the circulation of goods and passengers in various types of transport in our Republic, the total number of transported passengers is 5951.5 million passengers. 5,852.8 passengers or 98%, the total volume of transported cargo is 1,243.0 tons, of which 1,102.2 million tons or 88% is accounted for by road transport. determines how important the economy is. The largest share of transport services corresponds to the services of transportation of goods and passengers in road transport [5].

In January-March 2021, the share of passenger transportation services in road transport reached 67.7%. Compared to other types of transport, this type of transport is in high demand due to its flexibility and relatively low cost of the services provided. It is very important for motor transport enterprises (ATK) engaged in passenger transportation to organize their services efficiently, qualitatively and conveniently. This is mainly ensured by the careful and reliable organization of the main departments of the ATK [6].

Many researches and literatures have been conducted in our republic and foreign literature in order to increase the work efficiency of passenger transportation ATKs and optimize work processes. In particular, M.Z. Musajonov, M.A. Abduvaliyev, Q. M. Siddiqnazarov, M.A. Ikramov and others, the need to ensure the technical readiness of existing vehicles for the timely transportation of cargo and passengers at automobile enterprises at a high level, with the least expenditure and meeting environmental requirements, for this they are regularly it is emphasized that it is necessary to carry out maintenance and repair works (TCK and T), provide them with storage places, spare parts and materials related to auto operation, and perform a set of other services [7].

Foreign scientists G.V. Kramarenko, N.Ya. Govorushchenko have shown that the efficiency of motor transport enterprises depends on the level of organization of its technical service and current repair department, and how it is achieved through various theoretical and practical ways of improving engineering activities in this work. , B. S. Kleiner, E. S. Kuznetsova, N. P. Pankratova, I. Primakov, V. Chepurniy, and others. They discussed issues of improving the activities of engineering and technical workers with the participation of scientific research institutes and other production organizations. In order to provide high-quality and convenient service to customers, passenger transport companies first of all need to effectively

improve their performance, fundamentally re-equip the material and technical base, increase the rolling stock, update its composition and constantly improve its technical condition. It is necessary to emphasize two main strategic directions in improving the work efficiency of all cargo and passenger transport ATKs [8].

Improving the efficiency and optimization of the technical parameters of the traffic structure; - Improving the technology of efficient use of rolling stock in ATKs. In increasing and optimizing the technical parameters of the traffic structure, their technical maintenance and repair, technical control and diagnostics, at the same time, it is very important to have the professional competence of the person performing these works[9].

The production and technical base of any ATK consists of departments for maintenance and repair of rolling stock (TCK and T), storage. Their task is to ensure constant technical adjustment of cars, to maintain their technical parameters and to eliminate malfunctions during operation. All cargo and passenger ATKs will be equipped as per this requirement. In order to improve the efficiency and optimization of the technical parameters of the rolling stock in the TCK and T departments of ATK, it is necessary to provide the following: - to attract a qualified specialist with professional competence in the control and management of vehicle maintenance work and to organize the continuous improvement of the skills of employees ; - implementation of comprehensive measures for the prevention and elimination of technical malfunctions of cars during operation; - Provision of workshops and stations in TXK and T department with modern diagnostic and adjustment equipment; - Systematically and comprehensively carry out maintenance work on cars by type; - creating conditions in car storage areas that ensure that they do not lose their technical parameters[10].

The role of the control department is very important in improving the technology of efficient use of rolling stock in ATK. The time when the vehicles in the rolling stock leave the route, the correct organization of the movement intervals on the route, increasing the coefficient of technical preparation, the management of vehicle traffic on the route, the effective organization of the current repair of the vehicle in motion, and the effective organization of similar works The inspectors of the inspection department are determined by their professional competence and qualification. The provision of transportation services to passengers should be organized in such a way that all their requirements are met at the maximum level, at the lowest cost, and on time. Many foreign and domestic scientists have dealt with the problems of passenger service and its quality in urban public transport. Their scientific research works are devoted to the problems of improving the work of city public transport in various directions. Providing high-quality service is the most important issue in passenger transport. "Passenger service quality" means a set of transportation processes, a passenger transportation system that arises from meeting the demand for passenger transportation in accordance with the established regulatory requirements .

It is emphasized that in order to increase the efficiency of motor vehicles, more attention should be paid to improving their technical condition. This is an important issue, the main task in solving this is to give special importance to the technical service of motor transport enterprises. In this case, as the main task, it is necessary to implement comprehensive measures to ensure that the movement structure does not fail during operation and to prevent and eliminate them. The effectiveness of the activity of all departments in

the ATK depends on the professional skills of the employees working in this department, of course, the competence and qualification of the employees and technical engineers is the most important aspect in increasing the work efficiency.

At the same time, when researching the quality of public transportation services, they should be formulated based on the following principles: integrity, contingency, organization, incomprehensibility of complex systems (all indicators that determine the quality of transportation services cannot be evaluated individually) and therefore quantization of the system, decomposition, etc. If the standards determining the quality of the transport service to existing passengers are analyzed based on the principles of the system approach, the recognition that there are some serious shortcomings in the previous studies it is possible to achieve: - the fact that some factors affecting the quality of transport service provision are random in nature is not taken into account; - the decomposition principle of the systematic approach has not been widely used in the research of transport service provision processes.

For example, in researching the quality of transport service, considering the processes of "traffic organization" as a separate system, it has not been researched by dividing it into separate sub-systems.

CONCLUSION

It is very important to maintain and optimize the technical parameters of the traffic structure, to improve the technology of efficient use of cars, in order to increase the efficiency of the passenger transport vehicles. In order to organize these works, it is necessary to qualitatively organize the work of the TCK and T and control departments of ATK, to modernize and improve the production equipment base of the general enterprise.

All parameters are taken into account in the research of world scientists on the assessment of the quality of passenger transport services, but the issue of organizing the movement of rolling stock in the direction has not been sufficiently studied.

Taking into account the random nature of the transport service quality variable indicators, it is necessary to develop a method of ensuring their normative value. Capacity utilization factor is one of the most important factors affecting the quality of passenger transport services in city bus routes. That is, to standardize the coefficient of capacity utilization through indicators of the quality considered important (number of buses on the route, regularity of traffic, time spent by the passenger in the transport, capacity of the bus, etc.) it is possible to improve the quality of transport service to passengers.

To date, the analyzes of the indicators that affect the quality of transport services to passengers on bus routes carried out by scientists of the world and our country, made it possible to develop a scheme of dependence of the parameters that determine it on the coefficient of capacity utilization, and in turn, had a significant impact on the quality of the provided transport service. In the Andijan region, it is appropriate to give special importance to the organization of quality transport services for the population, especially to increase the number of buses and minibuses in the existing routes in the passenger transportation system and the fleet of vehicles moving in them.

In addition, in the management of the quality of transport services, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication systems, the equipping of bus stations and intermediate stations with modern equipment is one of the important elements of providing quality services to the population.

Today, extensive use of the experience of developed countries, the introduction of scientific and innovative developments in this field and further development of its promotion play an important role in the organization of quality transport services for the population.

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